

BINARY LESSONS AS A WAY TO CHANGE THE MOTIVATION OF STUDENTS STUDYING AT THE UNIVERSITY

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Annotation: *According to the authors, the use of new pedagogical technologies, for example, a binary practical lesson, contributes to a change in the motivation to study at a university and the formation of a more accurate idea of the profession.*

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An analysis of the current situation in the labor market indirectly indicates the insufficient effectiveness of the traditional educational paradigm, since when applying for a job, current graduates lack practical skills with a sufficiently high level of theoretical training. The transition to a new paradigm of education implies compensation for this gap in the training of specialists, but few specific tools (educational technologies) are offered to ensure a competency-based approach in education. Thus, the teaching staff finds itself in a situation of uncertainty, when, on the one hand, it is necessary to give out a significant amount of theoretical material, and on the other hand, to prepare a sought-after practitioner. The binary lesson model allows to combine the development of theory through its direct application in situations close to life, which contributes to the existing situation on the labor market for the better for graduates. An important component in the training of a specialist is his motivation for learning. If a student sees the prospects for applying the acquired knowledge in real life, then his motivation for learning increases, which affects the improvement of the assimilation of knowledge [2, 3]. According to the authors, a binary practical lesson, implemented within the framework of an activity approach, is inherently an interactive form of obtaining knowledge by students and eliminates the distance between theory and practice, but is used mainly in a general educational organization. The binary lesson model developed by the authors makes it possible to combine the acquisition of professional knowledge with the development of general cultural competencies among law students in accordance with the State Educational Standards of Higher Professional Education, the ability to generalize, analyze, perceive information, set a goal and choose ways to achieve it (OK-3), the ability to logically correctly, reasonably and clearly build oral and written speech (OK-4),

possessing a culture of behavior, readiness to cooperate with colleagues, work in the team (OK-5) [1].

It should be noted that in Universities binary classes are carried out mainly in the form of lectures in order to show the existence of different scientific views on the same problem. Binary practical exercises, in turn, involve combining game technologies, problem-based learning technologies, innovative technologies.

During the period of approbation of the model of binary classes for students of the 2nd year of the Faculty of Civil Engineering of the Tashkent State Transport University, TSTU, as part of the study of the discipline " Civil Engineering " from March to May 2022, a formative experiment was conducted using interactive classes using binary teaching technology, when the leaders of the business game and consultants are specialist constructors and specialist architectures. To improve the efficiency of mastering the content of the discipline, the authors used interactive forms of training (business games) on the topics " Architectural models " and "Responsibilities of contract discipline" with the involvement of students of technical and construction specialties. The total number of participants in the experiment is 58 people, of which 50 are male students and 8 are female students aged 18 to 21.

"Architectural models " is a complex discipline that involves the study of not only building, but also socio-psychological mechanisms for subsequent employment and effective enforcement practice. In a situation where it is necessary to apply the knowledge acquired at the university in the specialty, difficulties may arise due to insufficient development of communication skills. In other words, when applying for a job, students do not always adequately represent the needs and interests of a potential employer and are not able to demonstrate their knowledge and skills. The format of conducting classes proposed by the authors is aimed at developing the communicative competence of all participants in the educational process by simulating a real employment situation, terminating an employment contract and developing measures to comply with labor discipline in the team and bringing the employee to disciplinary responsibility.

To evaluate the effectiveness of this approach, the groups were divided into experimental and control groups. Psychodiagnostics testing was carried out with both groups before and after the experiment using the methodology for studying communicative and organizational inclinations "KOS" and the methodology for studying the motivation for learning at the university, as well as control testing of the knowledge gained by Civil engineering students on topics studied in an interactive form using test tasks for knowledge of the material. The experiment included three one and a half hour joint interactive practical classes in the form of a game.

As a result of the experiment in the experimental group, an insignificant increase in the average values of communicative and organizational inclinations (KOS method) was noted from 11.2 and 12.3 to 11.4 and 13.4, respectively; there was a slight decrease in the average values of motivation for obtaining a diploma (from 6.4

points to 5.7), which is interpreted by teacher as an inadequate motivation for studying at a university, the motives for acquiring knowledge were predominant in the motivation for learning , and the most stable were the motives for mastering a profession (5.3 points).

This means that by improving the communication skills of construction faculty students within the framework of the classes, we can influence the motivation for mastering the profession, creating a more complete picture of the real professional activity.

USED LITERATURE:

1. www.davarx.uz - Website of the State Committee for Architecture and Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
2. www.my.gov.uz - "Single portal of public services";
3. www.gov.uz- "Government portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
4. <http://www.Ziyo.net.uz> "